

Effects of Optimisation Techniques on Junior Secondary School Students' Academic Achievement in Mathematics in Ogbia Local Government Area, Bayelsa State

APREBO, Fiepre C.Y., Ph.D

Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education,
Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State.

aprebofc@fuotuo.ke.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18520122>

Abstract

The study assessed “the effects of optimization techniques on the academic achievement of junior secondary school students in mathematics in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State.” The study used “quasi-experimental, non-equivalent control group design.” The population comprised Junior Secondary School Two (JSS2) mathematics students in the area, with a sample of 112 students selected from two coeducational schools through purposive sampling. The experimental group was taught selected mathematics topics involving optimization problems using interactive optimization techniques such as problem-solving heuristics, real-life contextualised tasks, and graphical modelling, while the control group was taught using the conventional lecture method. The Mathematics Optimization Achievement Test on Optimization (MAOT), developed and validated by the researcher, was used for data collection. It had a reliability coefficient of 0.82 using the Kuder-Richardson 20 (KR-20) formula. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while independent sample t-tests were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed “a statistically significant difference in achievement in favour of the students exposed to optimization techniques.” Furthermore, “no significant gender difference was found among students taught using these techniques.” The study recommended that mathematics teachers should integrate optimization techniques into their instructional strategies to enhance students' achievement and promote deeper conceptual understanding.

Keywords: Optimization Techniques, Gender, Academic Achievement, Junior Secondary School Mathematics

Introduction

Mathematics remains a cornerstone in the educational development of every nation due to its integral role in science, technology, economics, and daily life. It underpins disciplines several prominent disciplines, thereby serving as a critical enabler of national development. As noted by Charles-Owaba (2018), a strong foundation in mathematics enhances students' logical reasoning, analytical skills, and access to several academic and career opportunities. The National Policy on Education (NPE, 2014) affirms this significance by making mathematics compulsory at primary and secondary schools, which underscores the necessity for teaching approaches that promote comprehension and academic success in the subject.

Despite the foundational role of mathematics in junior secondary education, students' performance in the Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE), commonly referred to as Junior WAEC, has continued to raise serious concerns among educators and stakeholders. The National Examinations Council (NECO) BECE Report (2021) revealed that a significant proportion of

students failed to attain credit-level passes in mathematics, with less than 50% scoring above the minimum benchmark. The Bayelsa State Ministry of Education (2022) also reported consistent underperformance in mathematics across public junior secondary schools, attributing it to poor comprehension of basic concepts, weak arithmetic foundations, and lack of application-oriented teaching. According to Eze and Obioma (2020), problem-solving tasks and algebraic expressions posed the most difficulties for candidates, reflecting a gap between curriculum expectations and classroom delivery. Furthermore, rigid, non-interactive teaching styles, coupled with students' math-related anxiety and poor learning environments, have been identified as major impediments to improved outcomes in junior mathematics examinations (Okoro & Ugwu, 2021).

Traditional teaching methods that rely predominantly on rote learning and teacher-centered instruction have been criticized for failing to actively engage students or foster deep understanding (Olunoye, 2020). These conventional approaches often leave students with fragmented knowledge and limited problem-solving skills, especially in topics that require logical sequencing and critical thinking (Basturk & Yavuz, 2020). In response to these challenges, scholars have advocated for innovative teaching strategies which encourages active learning and cognitive development. One such promising approach is the use of optimisation techniques in teaching mathematics.

Optimization techniques are structured problem-solving strategies that emphasize logical analysis, efficient decision-making, and application of mathematical principles to real-life situations. These techniques are commonly used in operations research and decision science, but they have increasingly found relevance in mathematics education. According to Nguyen and Walker (2019), optimization-based instruction helps students to explore multiple solution paths, evaluate outcomes, and refine their approaches, thereby strengthening conceptual understanding and analytical thinking. When applied in the classroom, these techniques can bridge abstract mathematical theories and practical application, making mathematics more meaningful and accessible to learners.

Empirical evidence supports the notion that problem-solving approaches, including linear programming, heuristic modelling, and graphical optimization, improve students' academic achievement by promoting engagement and deeper understanding (Singh & Issac, 2020). For instance, Duru and Agwagah (2018) found that "students taught mathematics using problem-solving frameworks showed significantly higher retention and performance than those exposed to conventional lecture methods." These findings suggest that integrating optimization techniques into mathematics instruction could address long-standing issues of poor achievement, particularly in the Nigerian junior secondary school context.

Also, research on gender and mathematics achievement reveals mixed findings. While some studies indicate that male students perform better in tasks requiring spatial and logical reasoning (Abiam & Odok, 2016), others argue that when instructional methods are adapted to students' needs, gender differences become negligible (Amelink, 2019). This indicates that optimization techniques, which emphasize structured reasoning and inclusive problem-solving, may offer equitable learning opportunities for both genders, potentially narrowing existing gender gaps in mathematics achievement.

Despite growing global emphasis on innovative strategies in mathematics education, studies focusing on the specific effects of optimization techniques at the junior secondary level in Nigeria remain limited. Most existing research has concentrated on general problem-solving skills or higher-level mathematics, with minimal attention to how optimization techniques influence foundational learning outcomes in junior secondary school students (Okafor & Okoye, 2022).

Given the foundational importance of junior secondary mathematics and students' persistent underachievement in the subject, it becomes crucial to examine instructional strategies that can enhance academic outcomes and foster equitable learning experiences.

This study, therefore, investigated "the effects of optimization techniques on the academic achievement of junior secondary school students in mathematics in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State." The study aims to determine how optimization-based instruction impacts students' learning outcomes, as well as to explore potential gender-based differences. The findings are expected to provide empirical evidence to guide educators, curriculum developers, and policymakers on effective strategies for improving mathematics achievement in Nigerian schools.

Statement of the Problem

Despite growing global emphasis on innovative strategies in Mathematics Education, studies focusing on the specific effects of optimization techniques at the junior secondary level in Nigeria remain limited. Most existing research has concentrated on general problem-solving skills or higher-level mathematics, with minimal attention to how optimization techniques influence foundational learning outcomes in junior secondary school students (Okafor & Okoye, 2022). Given the foundational importance of junior secondary mathematics and students' persistent underachievement in the subject, it becomes crucial to examine instructional strategies that can enhance academic outcomes and foster equitable learning experiences.

Empirical Review

Empirical evidence from numerous studies consistently demonstrates that the application of optimization techniques in mathematics instruction leads to improved achievement among junior secondary school students when compared with conventional teaching methods. Studies by Okoro and Chukwu (2018), Bature and Atweh (2019), Adewale and Kolawole (2021), and Yusuf and Busari (2017) revealed that structured lesson sequencing, optimized time management, problem-solving models, and visual-concept mapping significantly enhanced students' understanding and performance in mathematics. Similarly, Enyi and Uzoechi (2022), Akpan and James (2020), Ibrahim and Garba (2016), and Eze and Obasi (2018) reported that instructional content optimization, cognitive task structuring, and algorithmic approaches improved clarity, engagement, and retention, resulting in higher mean achievement scores. Further studies by Lawal and Bello (2020), Musa and Dogo (2021), Umeh and Ezenwa (2022), and Bashir and Gambo (2019) reinforced these findings by showing that optimized collaboration, adaptive learning paths, flipped classrooms, and time-segmented lessons consistently produced superior academic outcomes compared to traditional methods. Despite these consistent findings across various Nigerian states and mathematics topics, there is limited empirical evidence specific to schools in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State, thereby justifying the need for this study in that context. Therefore, the first research question is: "what is the difference in mean achievement scores between students taught mathematics using optimization techniques and those taught using conventional methods?"

While many studies have established the overall effectiveness of optimization techniques in improving mathematics achievement, empirical findings on gender-related differences remain limited and inconclusive. Most reviewed studies, including those by Okonkwo and Adeoye (2020), Chika and Olayemi (2019), Yahaya and Abdulrahman (2020), Ekpenyong and James (2022), and Danjuma and Suleiman (2023), primarily focused on aggregate achievement gains without explicitly disaggregating results by gender. However, studies such as Enyi and Uzoechi (2022) and Musa and Dogo (2021) suggest that optimized, differentiated, and adaptive instructional

approaches may reduce performance gaps by accommodating individual learning needs, which could potentially influence male and female students differently. Given existing concerns about gender disparities in mathematics achievement and the absence of clear empirical consensus on whether optimization techniques favor one gender over the other, it becomes necessary to examine gender-based differences within optimized instructional settings. Therefore, the second question is: “what is the difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using optimization techniques?”

Purpose of the Study

The study examined “the effects of optimization techniques on the academic achievement of junior secondary school students in mathematics in Ogbia Local Government Area of Bayelsa State.” Specifically, it determined:

- i. The difference in mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using optimization techniques and those taught using conventional methods.
- ii. The difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using optimization techniques.

Research Question

The following research questions guided the study:

- What is the difference in mean achievement scores between students taught mathematics using optimization techniques and those taught using conventional methods?
- What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using optimization techniques?

Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using optimization techniques and those taught using conventional methods.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using optimization techniques.

Methodology

The study used “pre-test, post-test, non-equivalent control group quasi-experimental design.” This design was appropriate as it allowed the investigation of effects of optimization techniques on students’ mathematics achievement within natural classroom settings. The use of intact classes made random assignment of students impracticable, as that approach could disrupt normal school routines and create artificial learning situations. The design therefore provided a realistic basis for comparing the achievement of students taught mathematics using the strategies, as well as for examining gender-based differences in achievement among students exposed to optimization techniques.

All pupils enrolled in the 34 state-owned secondary schools in Bayelsa State's Ogbia LGA made up the study's population. The research included a sample of 112 pupils from Junior Secondary School Two (JSS2). Two co-educational public secondary schools were purposively chosen as they possessed necessary instructional facilities and teaching personnel familiar with the implementation of optimization techniques in mathematics instruction. The JSS2 class was deliberately chosen since students at this level were not preparing for any external examinations, thereby allowing uninterrupted participation in the study, and because the mathematics topics at this level align well with the optimization strategies investigated.

Intact JSS2 classes were used at a few chosen schools. The classes were divided into the experimental and control groups using simple random selection by voting. Random assignments

were made to place one intact class from each school in the experimental group and the other in the control group. While the control group received education on the same subjects using the traditional way, the experimental group received instruction based on optimization techniques. The study's sample consisted of every JSS2 student in the chosen intact classrooms.

The researcher's "Mathematics Optimization Achievement Test (MOAT)" functioned for data collection. The MOAT was divided into two sections: Part I collected respondents' personal data, including gender, age, and school, while Part II included thirty multiple-choice questions intended to gauge students' comprehension of mathematical subjects where optimization methods are relevant. The items covered word problems involving number relationships, perimeter and area optimization, volume and surface area problems, simple linear programming concepts, arithmetic reasoning and resource allocation tasks, as well as time and work-related problems. The items were structured in line with the JSS2 Mathematics curriculum prescribed by the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) and adapted from past Junior WAEC Mathematics examinations. Each item had four options, and scored two marks, giving a total obtainable score of 60 marks.

The MOAT received face and content validation by experts who examined the instrument for relevance, clarity of language, adequacy of content coverage, and appropriateness of difficulty level for JSS2 students. A sample lesson note on optimization techniques was also provided to ensure alignment with the NERDC curriculum. Based on the experts' suggestions, necessary modifications were made to improve item clarity and content accuracy, thereby establishing the validity of the instrument.

A trial test at a junior secondary school outside the research region but with comparable features to the sampled schools was used to assess the MOAT's dependability. The experimental testing included twenty (20) JSS2 pupils. Since the items were scored dichotomously, the Kuder-Richardson Formula 20 (KR-20) was used to evaluate the data. The instrument was found to be adequately dependable for the investigation, as shown by the reliability coefficient of 0.79.

Pre-test, treatment, and post-test were the three phases of the experiment. Both groups took the MOAT during the pre-test phase to ascertain their starting mathematical proficiency. During the treatment stage, the experimental group received instruction using structured optimization techniques, while the control group received instruction using the conventional method. The treatment lasted for three weeks, with instructional activities carried out during the first and third weeks. After treatment period, the MOAT was re-administered as a post-test to determine the effect of the intervention. Separate lesson notes were prepared for the two groups to ensure uniformity of content coverage while varying only the instructional approach.

Version 26 of the "Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS)" was used to analyze the study's data. To address the study questions, descriptive statistics such as mean (\bar{x}) and standard deviation (SD) were used. Inferential statistics using independent samples t-test were used to test the hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the difference in mean achievement scores between students taught mathematics using optimization techniques and those taught using conventional methods?

Table 1: Mean Achievement Scores and Standard Deviation of Students Taught mathematics using optimization techniques and those taught using conventional methods

Groups	N	Pre-Gat		Post-Gat		Mean Gain
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Experimental	56	39.63	9.65	49.38	10.74	9.75
Control	56	39.58	9.01	43.49	10.80	3.91

The experimental group, which consists of students who were taught mathematics using optimization techniques, received a mean achievement score of 39.63 (SD = 9.65) in the Pre-GAT and a mean achievement score of 49.38 (SD = 10.74) in the Post-GAT, according to Table 1. In the Pre-GAT, the control group's (taught using conventional method) mean achievement score was 39.58 (SD = 9.01), but in the Post-GAT, it was 43.49 (SD = 10.80). The experimental group's mean gain was 9.75, whereas the control group's was 3.91. This suggests that pupils who were taught mathematics using optimization strategies outperformed the other group.

Research Question 2: What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using optimization techniques?

Table 2: Mean Achievement Scores and Standard Deviation of Male and Female Students Taught mathematics using optimization techniques

Gender	N	Pre Gat		Post-Gat		Mean Gain
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Male	47	39.14	8.86	45.61	10.70	6.47
Female	65	39.94	9.65	47.03	11.46	7.09

According to Table 2, male students who were taught mathematics utilizing optimization approaches had mean achievement scores of 45.61 (SD = 10.70) in the Post-GAT and 39.14 (SD = 8.86) in the Pre-GAT. The Pre-GAT mean achievement score for female students was 39.94 (SD = 9.65), whereas the Post-GAT mean achievement score was 47.03 (SD = 11.46). Male and female students' respective mean gains were 6.47 and 7.09. This shows that after learning optimization strategies, both male and female students improved, although female students' mean increase was somewhat larger than that of their male counterparts.

Testing Hypotheses

Ho₁: “There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using optimization techniques and those taught using conventional methods.”

Table 3: t-test analysis on the difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using optimization techniques and those taught using conventional methods

Category	N	X	St.D	d _f	p	t	Sig.	Decision
Experimental	56	41.53	9.61	110	0.05	1.67	0.000	Reject Ho ₁
Control	56	44.51	9.84					

Source: Fieldwork (2025)

At 110 degrees of freedom and a significance threshold of 0.05, Table 3 displays the computed t-value of 1.67. The p-value that corresponds to this is 0.000. The null hypothesis (Ho₁) is rejected since the p-value (0.000) is less than the alpha threshold of 0.05. This suggests “there is a statistically significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics using optimization techniques and those taught using conventional methods”

Ho₂: “There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using optimization techniques.”

Table 4: Independent t-test analysis on difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using optimization techniques

Category	N	X	St.D	df	p	t	Sig.	Decision
Male	25	42.37	9.42	54	0.05	.590	0.556	Accept Ho ₂
Female	31	43.49	10.10					

Source: Fieldwork (2025)

The computed t-value at 54 degrees of freedom and a 0.05 threshold of significance is 0.590, as Table 4 demonstrates. 0.556 is the associated p-value. The null hypothesis (Ho₂) is accepted since the p-value (0.556) is higher than the alpha threshold of 0.05. This suggests that 'the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics utilizing optimization approaches do not vary statistically significantly.'

Discussion of Findings

The findings revealed "students taught using optimization techniques recorded a higher mean gain than those taught with the conventional method." Specifically, students in the experimental group achieved a mean gain of 9.75, while those in the control group had a mean gain of 3.91, indicating a notable improvement in favour of the experimental group.

Further analysis through hypothesis testing supported this observation, showing a calculated t-value of 1.67 with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected, confirming that "there was a statistically significant difference in the mean achievement scores between the two groups." This suggests that "the use of optimization techniques had a positive and significant impact on mathematics achievement."

This finding agrees with the works of Enyi and Uzoechi (2022), Musa and Dogo (2021), Eze and Obasi (2018), who observed that students taught with innovative, problem-solving, and model-based strategies such as optimization methods, technology-enhanced instruction, or visual approaches outperformed those taught with conventional techniques. These studies emphasized that such techniques promote deeper conceptual understanding, critical thinking, and engagement, which contribute significantly to academic improvement in mathematics.

The findings on gender and students' achievement in mathematics using optimization techniques revealed that "female students had a slightly higher mean gain (7.09) compared to their male counterparts (6.47)." This indicates a marginal difference. However, the independent t-test analysis showed that this difference was not statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted, indicating that "there is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics using optimization techniques."

This finding agrees with studies such as those conducted by Chika and Olayemi (2019) Musa and Dogo (2021), Eze and Obasi (2018) who reported that technology-oriented and problem-solving instructional strategies tend to eliminate gender disparities in students' mathematics achievement. These researchers argued that such pedagogies offer equal cognitive engagement and learning experiences to both male and female students, making them equally capable of mastering mathematical concepts.

The finding implies that optimization techniques are gender-neutral and can effectively enhance students' performance in mathematics regardless of gender. This supports the adoption of inclusive and equitable instructional strategies that cater to learners' need in mathematics education.

Conclusion

According to the study's findings, teaching mathematics using optimization approaches improved students' performance more than the traditional lecture approach. Students who received teaching utilizing optimization approaches outperformed their peers who received instruction using the conventional way by a wide margin. This suggests that optimization techniques have a favorable impact on students' comprehension and mathematical ability. Additionally, the research discovered that the performance disparity between gender was reduced when optimization approaches were used. The difference in the mean scores was not statistically significant, this, optimization-based teaching promotes inclusive and successful mathematics education by giving all students, regardless of gender, equal learning opportunities.

Recommendations

- i. Mathematics teachers should adopt optimization techniques as a regular instructional strategy in teaching mathematical concepts, as it has been shown to significantly improve students' achievement.
- ii. Educational authorities arrange workshops and training sessions to build teachers' capacity in the effective use of optimization strategies and innovative pedagogical approaches that promote gender-inclusive mathematics instruction.

References

- Abiam, P. O., & Odok, J. K. (2016). Gender and mathematics achievement among senior secondary school students in Cross River State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 4(2), 121–130.
- Adeoye, A., & Okonkwo, E. (2020). Effects of heuristic-based optimization techniques on problem-solving performance in junior secondary mathematics. *Journal of Mathematics Education*, 11(2), 88–97.
- Adewale, A., & Kolawole, O. (2021). Time-task optimization strategies and mathematics performance among junior secondary students in Lagos State. *African Journal of Educational Research*, 14(1), 33–41.
- Akpan, M. U., & James, I. (2020). Enhancing junior secondary students' performance in number and numeration through cognitive task optimization. *International Journal of Educational Innovation*, 9(3), 54–62.
- Alabi, J. A., & Adebayo, O. M. (2017). Assessment-driven instructional optimization and mathematics achievement of junior students in Oyo State. *Journal of Assessment and Instructional Practices*, 6(2), 101–110.
- Amelink, C. T. (2019). Gender differences in mathematics achievement: Exploring instructional influences. *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*, 9(1), 58–66. <https://doi.org/10.5590/JERAP.2019.09.1.05>
- Bashir, H., & Gambo, S. (2019). Time optimization techniques in mathematics instruction: An experimental approach. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Psychology*, 8(1), 77–86.
- Basturk, R., & Yavuz, A. (2020). Effectiveness of teaching mathematics through real-life problems. *International Journal of Contemporary Educational Research*, 7(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.33200/ijcer.706303>
- Charles-Owaba, T., & Nwosu, M. (2022). Students' difficulties in learning geometry: Implications for instructional practices in Nigerian schools. *Journal of Educational Innovations*, 11(1), 22–31.

- Chika, P., & Olayemi, S. (2019). Visual-spatial optimization techniques in geometry teaching at the junior secondary level. *West African Journal of Education*, 11(4), 112–123.
- Ekpenyong, E., & James, A. (2022). Task-size optimization and academic achievement in number operations in Cross River State. *Journal of Curriculum and Instructional Design*, 13(1), 67–75.
- Enyi, D., & Uzoechi, B. (2022). Differentiated instructional optimization and its effect on academic performance in junior mathematics classrooms. *International Journal of Educational Practice*, 10(2), 89–97.
- Eze, S., & Obasi, C. (2018). Instructional content optimization and mathematics achievement among JSS2 students in Abia State. *African Journal of Educational Technology*, 7(1), 45–52.
- Ibrahim, M., Santos, J., & Lee, C. K. (2017). Impact of optimization-based teaching strategies on students' performance in mathematics. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 82, 112–121. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2016.02.004>
- Ibrahim, U., & Garba, M. (2016). Algorithmic optimization strategies and performance in solving linear equations. *Nigerian Journal of Mathematical Pedagogy*, 5(2), 34–42.
- Lawal, T., & Bello, R. (2020). Impact of optimized collaborative learning strategies on academic achievement in algebraic expressions. *Journal of Pedagogical Research*, 9(3), 91–100.
- Musa, L., & Dogo, A. (2021). Learning path optimization and achievement in basic mathematics operations. *Journal of Educational Strategies*, 12(1), 25–33.
- Nguyen, L., & Walker, K. (2019). Using optimization techniques to improve students' critical thinking in mathematics classrooms. *Journal of Mathematics Education*, 12(3), 75–86.
- Nwosu, C., & Onwuka, M. (2021). Learning resource optimization and academic performance in algebra. *Imo Journal of Education*, 14(2), 47–55.
- Okafor, C. N., & Okoye, K. R. E. (2022). Instructional strategies for enhancing students' performance in junior secondary school mathematics in Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Methodology*, 5(1), 89–98.
- Okoro, C., & Chukwu, B. (2018). Instructional optimization strategies and mathematics achievement of junior secondary school students in Rivers State. *Nigerian Journal of Instructional Delivery*, 9(2), 76–85.
- Olagunju, A. M., & George, J. O. (2015). Gender analysis of students' academic achievement in mathematics using interactive learning approach. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(30), 20–27.
- Olunoye, S. O. (2020). Pedagogical challenges in mathematics education and their implications for national development. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 11(29), 80–88.
- Schunk, D. H., & Zimmerman, B. J. (1998). *Self-regulated learning: From teaching to self-reflective practice*. Guilford Press.
- Umeh, R., & Ezenwa, I. (2022). Flipped classroom and instructional optimization for JSS students' statistics performance. *Anambra Journal of Mathematics Education*, 13(1), 59–67.
- West African Examinations Council (WAEC). (2020). *Chief Examiners' Report on Mathematics for May/June WASSCE*. Lagos: WAEC Press.
- Yahaya, M., & Abdulrahman, S. (2020). Instructional sequencing optimization and mathematics achievement in junior schools. *Middle Belt Journal of Educational Research*, 8(2), 84–91.

- Yilmaz, R. M., Yilmaz, F. G. K., & Cagiltay, K. (2022). Impact of artificial intelligence-supported mathematics teaching on students' academic success. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 38(1), 51–60. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcal.12590>
- Yusuf, A., & Busari, T. (2017). Optimization-based instructional packages and student achievement in geometry. *Journal of Mathematics Teaching Strategies*, 6(1), 41–50.
- Zimmerman, B. J. (2002). Becoming a self-regulated learner: An overview. *Theory into Practice*, 41(2), 64–70. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15430421tip4102_2